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STAGE OF EYELID EPITHELIAL TUMORS
(on the example of Khorezm region).

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Abstract: This article is devoted to the study of the incidence, clinical and morphological characteristics, and structural types of eyelid epithelial tumors among eye diseases among the population of the Khorezm region. The research material was formed by biopsy and post-surgical materials from patients diagnosed in specialized medical institutions of the region in 2024–2025, as well as morphological analysis using histological and standard staining methods.

According to the obtained results, it was found that among eyelid epithelial tumors, basal cell cancer takes the leading place, tumors are more common in the elderly age group and in people with high sun exposure. It was also noted that there are regional peculiarities in the localization of tumors, growth characteristics and degree of malignancy. The results of the research are important for early diagnosis of eyelid tumors, improvement of preventive measures and application in practical ophthalmopathology and pathomorphology.

Relevance of the topic: In general, solar radiation, environmental factors, decreased immunity in the human body and age factors play an important role in the development of these tumors. Therefore, in-depth study of the morphological and immunohistochemical characteristics of epithelial tumors is an important role in the development of early diagnosis and effective treatment tactics. Today, among ophthalmological diseases, eyelid epithelial tumors account for approximately 85–90% of all eyelid tumors. Although benign tumors also account for the majority of them, malignant tumors (especially basal cell carcinoma) are one of the most common diseases encountered in clinical practice.

Systematic local data on the incidence, morphological types, and clinical features of eyelid epithelial tumors among the population of the Khorezm region are lacking. Most of the available studies are limited to general statistical data and do not sufficiently reveal regional epidemiological and pathomorphological characteristics, which creates certain difficulties in early diagnosis and development of effective treatment tactics for these diseases.

From this point of view, a comprehensive study of the incidence, morphological structure, and clinical significance of eyelid epithelial tumors in the Khorezm region is relevant. The obtained results serve to improve early diagnostic criteria, plan preventive measures, and develop practical recommendations for ophthalmologists and pathomorphologists.

Purpose of the study: To study the clinical and statistical aspects of eyelid epithelial tumors among the population of the Khorezm region.

Research materials and methods: Biopsies and post-surgical materials from patients who underwent surgery for eyelid tumors were studied as research materials.

Research results: According to the results of the research, when the patients were divided by gender, the total number of patients was 95, of which 45 (47.3%) were men and 50 (52.6%) were women (see diagram 1).

Diagram 1. Distribution of patients by gender.

As can be seen in the diagram, among the diseases, a higher rate was recorded in women than in men, namely 53%.

During the research, the addresses of patients were studied and 15 people in Urganch city, 10 people in Urganch district, 10 people in Khiva city, 7 people in Khazorasp district, 6 people in Pitnak district, 5 people in Khanka district, 9 people in Bogot district, 7 people in Yangiariq district, 9 people in Yangibozor district, 3 people in Gurlan district, 8 people in Shavot district, 6 people in Koshkopir district. See diagram 2.

Diagram 2. Meeting of patients in cities and districts.

In diagram 2, among ophthalmological diseases, eye epithelial tumor diseases are more common in Urganch than in other cities and districts (15 people).

Overall, basal cell carcinoma was the most common type of epithelial eyelid neoplasm, occurring mainly in elderly patients. Among benign tumors, papilloma, keratoacanthoma, and seborrheic keratoses predominated (see Figure 3).

Figure 3. Occurrence of ophthalmological diseases.

As can be seen in diagram 3, among eye diseases, basal cell cancer was found to be the most common (40 cases).

Conclusion: In conclusion, it can be said that 1. Basal cell carcinoma is the most common malignant tumor among epithelial tumors of the eyelid. 2. The results obtained serve to improve differential diagnosis and treatment tactics in clinical practice. 3. The results of the study showed a high incidence of eyelid epithelial tumors among the population of the Khorezm region and that this pathology has certain clinical, morphological and epidemiological characteristics. 4. Among eyelid tumors, epithelial tumors predominated, with basal cell carcinoma accounting for the majority. This may be due to the climatic conditions of the region, especially the high level of solar radiation. 5. The study revealed that the tumors are more common in the elderly and are localized in the lower eyelid. It was noted that the slow growth of malignant tumors over a long period of time and the low severity of symptoms in the early stages are important factors leading to late diagnosis. 6. The obtained results indicate the need for early diagnosis of epithelial tumors of the eyelid, mandatory use of morphological examinations and strengthening of preventive examinations. Research conclusions are important in practical ophthalmology and pathomorphology, as well as in improving the regional oncology service.

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